

PROFESSION MISTAKES IN THE ACTIVITY OF A TEACHER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403223>

Abstract. *The complexity and subtlety of the pedagogical error in most cases without being realized by the pedagogue, the errors related to the strategy of the pedagogical activity, the elimination of the errors in the planning of the pedagogical activity are covered in this article.*

Keywords: *pedagogical error, cooperation, tactical errors, pedagogical process, educational material.*

Errors are a typical phenomenon that occurs in all areas of human activity. Therefore, any pedagogical activity is not free from mistakes, but it is observed that the cost of mistakes made in this field is very expensive for others, and it is painful. Because pedagogical mistakes can cause tragic consequences for a whole person (child).

The complexity and subtlety of the pedagogical error is characterized by the fact that the pedagogue does not realize it in most cases. It is this situation that does not leave the possibility to prevent it or draw a correct conclusion from it. By the time the consequences of a mistake become apparent, it is too late to correct the mistake, or it becomes obvious that it will have no effect.

Mistakes can be made in the form of actions, habits, reactions during cooperation with students during the period of predicting the future pedagogical activity, as well as during the implementation of the direct pedagogical process.

Errors in the strategy (prediction) of pedagogical activity include errors in goal setting and errors in planning the educational process.

Errors related to setting pedagogical goals:

1. As a result of the teacher's failure to properly understand the essence of pedagogical activity, the lesson process is carried out without certain predetermined goals, as a result, the training is organized on the basis of a random goal that arose directly in the course of the lesson, and extremely low efficiency in education is achieved.

As a result of the inconsistency of methodological goals, achieving a low quality-indicator through the failure of logical connections at different stages of the lesson.

The reasons for the recognized errors are characterized by the inability of the pedagogue to plan his training clearly and carefully in advance, that is, the inability to set specific internal educational and pedagogical goals.

In order to prevent such mistakes, the pedagogue should first of all have a perfect knowledge of his specialty, secondly, a deep understanding of the spiritual life of society and social tasks, thirdly, he should know the interests of children well and be able to direct them to educational goals, and most importantly, he should be able to perfectly define the goals of educational activities will be done. For this, the teacher will have to be specially engaged in mastering the methodology of setting educational goals.

Errors in the planning of pedagogical activities are closely related to errors in setting the purpose of training, and they appear in a synchronous manner. It is advisable to analyze the process related to these errors in depth, to determine their true nature, to divide them into separate groups.

Tactical mistakes are mistakes characterized by pedagogical cooperation, communication, organization process and going beyond the scope of etiquette. Also, the following types of errors associated with didactic influence are found:

a) errors of a methodological nature determined by the teaching of subjects directly related to the subject he teaches;

b) errors related to the organization of children's educational activities (pedagogical management) in the course of the lesson.

Errors of a methodological nature determined by the teaching of subjects directly related to the subject taught by the teacher, such as confusion in their explanation, lack of system, excessive complexity of the teacher's speech, extreme emotionality in the delivery of educational material or lack of it, inability to properly allocate class time, inability to choose educational methods and purposeful use of technical tools based on circumstances.

Therefore, scientists classify mistakes related to pedagogical cooperation as methodological defects of pedagogues. Since the errors listed in V.I.Juravlev's book "Basics of Pedagogical Conflictology" are expressed by the student, it allows the teacher to look at himself from the "outside" as a direct participant in the educational process.

The errors listed in V.I.Juravlev's book "Basics of Pedagogical Conflictology" are of particular importance because they are identified by children.

V. I. Juravlev especially acknowledges the indecision during the evaluation of the students' knowledge, among the mistakes of the teachers identified by the students during the lesson.

Students will pay special attention to the following aspects related to this process:

- encourage children to answer in a non-standard way and require them to answer in the form and order specified in the program and standard or in the way they want;

- teenagers in most cases expressed their displeasure with the fact that the teachers gave the child an unsatisfactory grade without asking the reason why he did not do his homework;

- the children also mentioned that it hurt their feelings when the teachers gave long admonitions to the students for the wrong answer or scolded the students for going astray from the correct answer.

The reasons for the dissatisfaction of teenagers are also shown to be:

- sudden control work without prior warning;

- there is no room for jokes in classes, the student's refusal to answer the teacher's question or his/her expression of not being ready for the lesson is greeted by the teacher's nervous shouting;

- checking or requesting homework assignments, etc.

The well-known Russian pedagogue V. N. Soroka-Rosinsky criticized some adventurous pedagogues in their time for the fact that they emphasized and tried to implement what caught their attention or what they wanted in the training they conducted with "good" intentions. Teachers of this category tend to use unproven methods arbitrarily without the advice of the school administration or experienced pedagogues, make various unjustified changes to the educational content. In most cases, instead of textbooks and topics recommended by methodical centers and methodical councils, they require students to master materials based on their own outlines or developments. In their eyes, non-standard methods of teaching science require just such an approach.

In conclusion, it can be said that pedagogical mistakes should be accepted as a unique component of the pedagogical process. Taking into account the recognized circumstances, we will

dwell on some recommendations for the prevention of pedagogical-professional mistakes or their elimination. Is it possible to doubt the effectiveness of the methods and technologies you use in your daily pedagogical activities in connection with your profession? Get into the habit of systematically analyzing from the point of view of hesitate, doubt. Get used to looking at yourself through the eyes of others in the process of pedagogical activity. Try to debate and argue with the thoughts and views that you have. Keep a journal and regularly record new thoughts and ideas that come to you.

Try to predict the consequences of your conclusions.

Try to diligently read and study all pedagogical, psychological and methodical literature related to the subject you teach. Do not get used to overestimating your personal experience, try to organize your private pedagogical activity on a scientific basis, not on the basis of rigid views, stereotypes, and narrow imaginations.

Keep an "error log". Treat them like a valuable commodity. Regularly reading the mistakes recorded in the notebook will teach you not to repeat them in the next activity.

Do not be afraid to make mistakes, accustom yourself to new ways of thinking. You cannot protect yourself from making mistakes through fear.

Be ready to formulate an alternative solution to the problem based on the correct assessment of the educational situation or situation that has arisen through analysis.

Generalization, reaching the final conclusion ("Even though I came to the seminar or practical training without any special preparation, I managed to get a good grade due to my abilities, knowledge and potential, so I can get high grades in any further training without appropriate training." etc.) try not to make mistakes.

Avoid following established routines, rigid stereotypes, and blind imitation. Do not get into the habit of accepting any instructions or opinions from others, even your teachers, for execution, information and execution without critically analyzing your own prism. Try to be as critical as possible about any information and yourself. When evaluating someone or conveying certain information to others, especially to your colleagues, do not get into the habit of giving information or evaluation based on other people's (unproven, unreliable) opinions that you have never heard from others.

Do not take on the depression and negative situations of others, do not allow their behavior and behavior to cause you discomfort. Keep in mind that the root of such behavior and failure in people is their personal problems and inability to make appropriate changes by approaching their activities from a critical perspective.

Don't get discouraged if you make a mistake. Always try to develop your theoretical-intellectual level and potential and succeed.

Regularly observe the lessons of experienced pedagogues, try to learn new methods and unique aspects of creativity from them.

Pedagogues, who are masters of their profession, try not to make mistakes at all or to reduce them as much as possible. The teacher, as a subject of the educational process, regularly performs the activities of solving problems and tasks of various nature and complexity related to the content of education. It is impossible to be completely free from errors. However, it is possible to teach the teacher to behave correctly in real pedagogical conditions, to warn of possible mistakes and conflict situations or to prevent them.

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